

Developing a Co-Creation Makerspaces on Renewable Energy Technology for Children: Multi-Stakeholder Insights on Challenges and Solutions

Christian Stadlmann, Andrea Holzinger

*Christian Stadlmann, University of Applied Sciences Upper Austria
Steyr, Austria
christian.stadlmann@fh-steyr.at*

*Andrea Holzinger, University of Applied Sciences Upper Austria
Steyr, Austria
andrea.holzinger@fh-steyr.at*

Abstract

Purpose: This paper investigates the challenges and solutions in developing a co-creation makerspace initiative for children, focused on renewable energy technology.

Methodology/data: A comprehensive methodological approach was employed, combining case study analysis, reflection reports, and qualitative semi-structured interviews with 4 trainers and 4 key stakeholders involved in the initiative. Above, the study utilized the analytical framework provided by Mersand (2021).

Findings: The study identified several challenges, including pedagogical aspects, financial sustainability, workshop development, parental involvement, organizational issues, social and diversity barriers, and safety concerns. These challenges varied depending on the format of the sub-initiatives: permanent maker groups, school workshops, and summer events.

Research implications: The findings suggest that addressing these challenges requires tailored strategies for different formats, such as enhanced financial planning, improved communication, and inclusive practices. A list of potential countermeasures is provided. Further research should explore larger, diverse samples, comparative studies in various geographical settings, and longitudinal studies assessing long-term impacts.

Original value: This study contributes by providing insights into the case-specific challenges and solutions, highlighting the importance of context-related strategies, and elaborating differences to previous studies and novel elements. These insights may help other initiatives address common problems and enhance their effectiveness with the proposed solution approaches.

Keywords

Makerspace, Children, Challenges, Solutions, Permanent format

1 Introduction

The makerspace and fablab movements have enormously evolved over the last decades. Studies highlight three distinct phases since the early 2000s. In the beginning, makerspaces featured fabrication tools and 3D printers and were used mainly by adult hobbyists. Further on, the integration into formal education became common. Many schools and universities adopted makerspaces that used diverse materials to foster skills such as creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration (Soomro et al. 2023). In the last 10 years, study designs have shifted to child-specific environments equipped with advanced technologies. Additionally, studies in kindergarten and early school settings report improvements in digital

literacy, problem-solving, and creative design skills (Soomro et al. 2023). This shift to child-specific initiatives can also be found in practice in the region of Upper Austria. In the last decade new projects were started by companies, such as the Otelo initiative realized in companies such as Fill, MIBA or Mark, with the aim to support the region and assist them in early employer branding. Other maker ventures for children resulted from the cooperation of various companies and the local government, such as the BetaCampus. A lighthouse project was launched in the capital Linz in 2019 with the Grand Garage. Originally designed for adults, this makerspace with an area of 2000m² also began to carry out activities for children and young people right from the start.

It should be noted that there have long been on-spot initiatives such as the KinderUni. However, these are primarily planned and implemented for vacation care and short-term events. Inherent in all these initiatives, however, is the fact that the implementation of maker activities is associated with challenges (Peter Mylon et al. 2019).

2 Thematic Analysis of General Challenges of Makerspaces

When examining the challenges, barriers and possible solutions of children maker initiatives, a completely uniform picture does not emerge. The challenges depend on the setting (such as academic, school, company or community-based settings) and the embedding of the initiatives in the environmental conditions. Mersand (2021) categorizes the various settings along different possible frameworks.

Nevertheless, some challenges can be identified that are repeatedly mentioned in studies. Looking at the challenges of makerspaces or fab labs and solutions proposed, a categorization of the following topics can be drawn:

- Diversity and Inclusion Barriers
- Operational and Resource Challenges
- Pedagogical Aspects
- Community Engagement

2.1 Diversity and Inclusion Barriers

Gender representation emerges as a significant challenge across multiple studies. Greenberg & Barton (2017) identified a substantial gender imbalance in fabrication laboratories, with women participating less due to uninviting cultures and lack of role models. They observed a significant gender gap in maker culture despite the perceived inclusivity of these spaces. The challenges extend beyond gender to socioeconomic access. Barton et al. (2017) noted that the maker movement has not been broadly successful at involving a diverse audience, particularly over a sustained period. The study highlighted that makerspaces often reflect a white, middle-class approach, which may not resonate with youth from diverse backgrounds.

2.2 Operational and Resource Challenges

Operational and resource challenges occur chiefly in public or library settings. Budget constraints, space allocation difficulties, and regular equipment maintenance problems surface in studies such as those by Slatter & Howard (2013) and Moorefield-Lang (2014). Mylon et al. (2019) highlight that some initiatives face constraints related to safety regulations, risk management, the viability and scalability of operational models and governance structures.

2.3 Pedagogical Aspects

Concerning the pedagogical aspects of makerspaces, commonly referred key considerations are learning scaffolding, skill development and assessment challenges. Hereto, Einarsson & Hertzum (2019) identified seven ways of scaffolding learning across formal, non-formal, and informal activities in library makerspaces. They noted the challenge of balancing structured guidance with the freedom necessary to

maintain creativity and engagement. Adler-Beléndez et al. (2021) highlighted the potential of makerspaces for developing 21st-century skills such as collaboration, communication, critical thinking, and creativity. However, they also noted a lack of consensus on how effectively makerspaces contribute to these skills. Additionally, the authors pointed out the limited use of pre-post measures to assess learners' growth, suggesting difficulties in quantifying the educational impact of makerspace activities.

2.4 Community Engagement

Community engagement is the fourth category of frequently identified barriers. Particularly community-based makerspaces heavily depend on community support, membership fees and hence, must navigate local regulations and community expectations. Although they may have more flexibility than institutionalized initiatives, they need to organize the support continuously (Dreessen et al. 2016). Above, specific communities are difficult to reach due to this tension between financing and engagement. One goal of many community-based initiatives is to serve a more diverse demographic, including local entrepreneurs and disadvantaged community members. However, they struggle due to financial barriers with the actual integration and engagement of these groups (Rayna & Striukova, 2019).

3 Challenges and Solutions of Makerspaces for Children

In addition to the challenges that many makerspaces face, additional or special burdens can be identified for maker initiatives for children, whereby the design of the makerspace also has an influence here.

More specifically, initiatives for children in makerspaces face pedagogical, technical and resource-related challenges (Giusti & Bombiere, 2020). In education, studies report that curriculum integration problems occur with significant impact. Teachers struggle to align makerspace activities with formal curricula and strike a balance between structured learning and creative exploration, hampered by a lack of time and insufficient preparation (Salisbury & Nichols, 2020). In tech environments, children's lack of familiarity with complex digital manufacturing processes and inadequate infrastructure - such as unreliable Wi-Fi and limited computer access - are substantial barriers, while safety concerns and limited access to devices are identified, too (Giusti & Bombieri, 2020). Resource challenges include financial constraints and structural barriers that hinder accessibility for diverse learners, as well as concerns about staffing and expertise (Barton et al. 2017).

Some studies propose solutions for these barriers that basically follow three primary strategies. Pedagogical approaches, such as long-term engagement, interest-driven learning, collaborative projects, and reflective practices, have been implemented in varied settings to boost motivation and deepen learning (Barton et al. 2017). Safety and support improvements include structured safety protocols, mentorship programs, inclusive design, and professional development for educators to enhance confidence and skills (Bar-El & Zuckerman, 2016). Finally, resource optimization strategies—for example, community partnerships, modular and adaptable spaces, open-source resources, and recycling initiatives—aim to improve resource access and operational efficiency (Bar-El & Zuckerman, 2016).

Although studies show similarities, challenges are strongly influenced by the respective frameworks and situational factors. This study therefore aims to contribute to the previous findings by investigating a specific mixed project- and community-based maker initiative, called Junior Maker Pioneers, with a particular focus on renewable energy technology and identifying new or specifically different challenges and chosen solutions. The guiding questions of this study are therefore as follows:

- What specific challenges characterize the Junior Maker Pioneers initiative?
- How do they differ from other children's maker initiatives?
- What solutions were chosen for the various challenges?

4 Methodology

In this study a comprehensive methodological approach was employed, combining case study analysis, reflection report and qualitative interviews. The first step involved the detailed examination of the Junior Maker Pioneers initiative, that was launched in October 2023. This initiative was chosen due to its relevance, recent establishment and particular embedding. The case study was examined along the analytical framework provided by Mersand (2021), which includes the participants (subjects), tools, community, rules, division of labour, objectives, and outcome. The case study approach allowed for an in-depth understanding of the specific initiative, providing a foundation for further analysis.

In the second step, reflection reports were prepared by project organizers of the investigated initiative. These reports provided a systematic analysis of their experiences, challenges faced, and solutions implemented. The reflection reports offered a personal and managerial perspective.

To supplement and contrast the perspective of the project managers, qualitative semi-structured interviews were conducted with 4 trainers and 4 key-stakeholder, i.e. one manager of the adult makerspace serving as the home base for the initiative, one manager and one trainer of the workshops delivered to schools and being further responsible for summer workshops and one organizer of a digital children initiative executing the marketing activities of this case study. All key-stakeholders have been involved right from the initiative's conceptualization. The interviews were conducted online (3) or in-person (5) with a duration of 35-60 minutes in the period of February and March 2025. The interviews aimed to gather insights into the experiences, challenges, and solutions from those directly involved. All interviews were recorded and transcribed. Adhering to Mayring's (2022) guidelines, codes and categories through various coding phases, including initial and focused coding, were inductively generated to identify and group recurring themes emerging from the conversations. Finally, all collected data from the various methodological approaches were compared also with a focus on what of previous studies could be confirmed and what may be novel.

5 Case Study Junior Maker Pioneers (JMP)

This study draws on Mersand's (2021) analytical framework, which is grounded in activity theory and conceptualizes makerspaces through seven interconnected elements: *participants, tools, community, rules, division of labor, objectives, and outcomes*. These elements provided a systematic lens for structuring the case description and analysis. However, Mersand (2021) emphasize that the geographic location and the local conditions are strongly influencing this framework and the setting of a makerspace. Thus, a brief overview about the regional conditions and the start of the initiative are described.

Steyr is a mid-sized industrial city with approximately 40,000 inhabitants. Famous manufacturing companies, such as BMW, SKF, or ZF, have production sites in Steyr. In the Steyr region no publicly accessible, continuous maker activities for children were existing. A makerspace for adults only and a digital-coding initiative for children (Coderdojo) had been active for 5 and 7 years, both community-based and with many voluntary supporters. In the last years, regional manufacturers have started to focus on renewable energy technologies or have turned into renewable energy technology companies.

The focused case initiative started with an idea competition of the city of Steyr in which the principal proposal of establishing a maker possibility for kids was awarded in 2021. After various concepts failed due to financial hurdles or a lack of support, a 4-year co-creation space, called Junior Maker Pioneers (<https://junormakerpioneers.at/>), was applied for and finally selected by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (2023). With this co-funding the initiative has been able to start its activities for children and young people in project-based learning activities in October 2023. The following chapters describe the case initiative according to the analytical framework of Mersand (2021) based upon the expanded activity theory (Engeström, 2001).

5.1 Objectives

The basic idea of the initiative is that children develop an enthusiasm for technology and at the same time learn about sustainability from a technical perspective. The approach is to learn more about renewable energy technologies through manual making and vice versa to inspire children for making through the topic of “renewable energy technologies” in a playful way. Renewable energy technologies are broadly defined in terms of content, from energy production to finally green mobility, industry and living. Three main formats have been chosen for implementation: 1) Development and establishment of junior maker pioneer groups, in which the same children permanently meet to become young makers of renewable energy technologies analogous to the junior teams of sports clubs or scouts. 2) Inspired by the historical fractal production facilities of the city of Steyr, various existing facilities, such as companies, the local museum Arbeitswelt, schools, the university or the adult makerspace, are to be used for school workshops on the subject of “renewable energy technologies”. 3) Disseminating developed workshops also through the established summer workshop organizer KinderUni Upper Austria. In addition, the establishment of a pool of trainers and a dissemination platform shall help to lay the foundations for continuation beyond the project. Co-creativity should serve as a guideline for all activities.

5.2 Participants (Subjects), Tools and Workshops

The targeted children are 8-14 years of age which was recommended by other initiatives. The focus is put on manual making and deliberately not on digital activities for differentiation reasons and being complementary to the existing CoderDojo.

The principal idea is to use as much as possible existing infrastructure of core supporters, such as the adult makerspace in which a 40 m² room is rented, and to acquire step-by-step materials and tools demanded by workshops developers (such as soldering equipment, Japanese saws, cordless screwdrivers, pliers, ...) for the permanent groups. This approach to follow the needs of the workshops and not simply setting up the equipment first, is following the recommendation of Tufts university (Vizner, 2016). The homebase of the permanent group should have been the adult makerspace, offering the possibility to use special equipment in the case of urgent necessities. Workshops for schools or in summer through KinderUni have also been planned in existing facilities such as the local museum, university, adult makerspace, or companies.

In the beginning a co-creation workshop with teachers, makers, company representatives and experts of initiatives for children was conducted to understand the needs of the target groups (children and schools) and to create ideas for possible workshops. However, the final development and selection of workshops should be handed over to the trainers. Additionally, a network to other facilities, such as a textile lab of a local high school, the technical high school, the waste collection centre, was established and used for workshops. The topics were either directly linked to renewable energy technology or technology and technical skills needed for later thematic workshops.

5.3 Community, Division of Labor and Rules

The tasks were divided according to competences and expertise. The project applicant, the University of Applied Sciences Upper Austria, is responsible for all managerial tasks. Although there is no technical expertise in the faculty of Management in Steyr, its role is to be a facilitator, motivator, connector and financial manager (Martelloni et al. 2017). The trainers are recruited from the adult makerspace community, the university, from schools and from the parents of participating kids. Although the trainers are offered a small financial recognition for their efforts, this task is based on voluntary work. Additionally, all trainers and parents of the permanent groups get quasi free access to the adult makerspace with 24/7 availability financed by the project and the adult makerspace. Regular community building events, such as a Christmas drink, BBQ or a visit to other makerspaces were organised for trainers and parents. Continuous trainer meetings to clarify the semester program and to collect feedback were executed, too.

In the beginning, a safety concept was developed, and all trainers and parents need to do a safety training. Additionally, a liability insurance for all trainers was signed. Furthermore, collaboration rules for the kids were developed together with the trainers.

5.4 Outcomes

Within 13 months two permanent groups of 11 kids each were established and in total 31 different workshops were conducted. Additionally, excursions to companies were done. The activities for schools were bundled in action days, in which companies and makers offered workshops at the university or at the firms' premises. Further action days for schools will be offered as part of the exhibition "Energy Transition – Race against Time" of the close museum from 2025 onwards. Additional workshops were developed and conducted for the summer workshops of KinderUni. The most important desired result for the initiative is an affective one, namely, to arouse enthusiasm and interest in children for technology and environmental protection. The trainers further want to develop the children's knowledge (cognitive outcome) and skills with materials and tools (behavioral outcome) (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). This is reflected in the use of a wide variety of tools and topics in the workshops. However, the overarching goal is to transfer the project initiative into a permanent establishment.

Figure 1 summarizes the structural and pedagogical characteristics of the three formats of the project initiatives: permanent maker groups, school workshops, and summer workshops.

Figure 1: Characteristics of three formats of the project initiatives

Format	Duration	Frequency	Session Structure	Themes	Tasks	Goals	Interactions	Instructor Background
Permanent Maker Groups	Continuously throughout entire school year. 2 hours/session. Workshops consist of 1-3 sessions.	Weekly or bi-weekly continuously throughout entire year	Structured, over time with progressive content and recurring participants	Deepening technical/maker knowledge in renewable energy technologies topics	Complex: guided or unguided making, experimenting, iterative prototyping	Sustained interest, skill development, project ownership, long-term engagement, community building	Strong peer interaction, relationship with trainers, continuity	Makers, educators, parents, with long-term commitment
School Workshops	Action days organized in 2 weeks/semester. 2-3 hours/workshop	Single sessions or short sequences.	Compressed format with fixed schedule	Basic introduction to renewable energy technologies	Guided activities, short builds	Introduction to topic and motivation for further exploration	Short-term interaction, trainer-led, teacher supervised	Mostly freelance trainers
Summer Workshops	Half-day to full-day events during August	Irregular, based on availability	Compressed format with fixed schedule	Broad appeal topics with simplified content	Quick builds, playful exploration	Visibility, outreach, low-threshold engagement	Highly heterogeneous, spontaneous interactions	Varied; some new facilitators with little preparation

6 Findings on Challenges in Developing a Co-Creation Makerspaces on Renewable Energy Technology for Children

Combining the reflection reports and qualitative interviews various challenges of the investigated initiative for children on Renewable Energy Technology can be identified and categorized. Although the initiative is a single project based mainly on voluntary work, differences in the challenges crystallize along the 3 main approaches, namely the creation of permanent groups, the establishment of school workshops and further dissemination via summer education events. While some challenges were encountered across all formats, others were highly format-specific. Therefore, the categorization is split up into general overarching difficulties and hurdles of the 3 approaches. All challenges are developed for 1st and 2nd order constructs which are all available in the appendix.

6.1 Challenges Across All Formats

Two obstacles identified in previous studies were also encountered in all 3 formats (cf. Figure 2). One challenge is linked to pedagogical aspects rooted in the heterogeneity and varying levels of engagement among children. Trainers reported that children often appeared tired and unfocused, which hindered their ability to participate effectively in workshops. Additionally, children frequently felt overwhelmed due to the complexity of the tasks, and their lack of prior knowledge exacerbated this issue. Managing

different skill levels within a group proved to be remarkably challenging, as some children lacked motivation while others engaged in disruptive behavior. Some attention-seeking children often distracted their peers, and the presence of mobile phones further contributed to disruptions. Moreover, as children are eager to try things themselves, sometimes these actions led to chaos and hindered the development of creativity and problem-solving skills.

Secondly, all three approaches faced significant challenges related to financial sustainability. The current economic situation made it difficult to secure funding, and there was a constant tension between financing, volunteer work, and trainer satisfaction. Balancing the monetary needs of trainers with the available resources of the initiative was demanding, and expanding the initiative was constrained by limited resources. Organizers and stakeholders expressed concerns about the alignment of payment with long-term project goals, highlighting the difficulty in maintaining financial sustainability while meeting the minimum monetary expectations of trainers and volunteers.

6.2 Challenges in Permanent Maker Groups

While previous challenges identified in this study are partly known from prior research, the following specific issues emerged in the context of long-term maker groups. These challenges are rarely addressed in literature, which tends to focus on short-term, project-based activities and differ from other children's maker initiatives (cf. Figure 3).

The first specific hurdle related to the selection and development of workshops. Continuous innovation and the necessary development of new workshops within a short timeframe, led to a high preparation effort and hindered the reuse of complete workshops. This led to a certain dissatisfaction of trainers who often had false expectations regarding the preparation effort. Additionally, many workshop developing coaches were coming from the maker community, having high aspirations for the quality, level of difficulty and creativity of workshops, and rejecting standardized ready-to-use craft kits. The poor quality of external workshop templates, videos or descriptions, lacking sufficient information and clear explanations, impacted this attitude further. These in-house developments also meant that the new projects had to be additionally documented for later reuse, which in turn led to considerable effort for the trainers or simple missing documentation of projects. Additionally, the lack of available maker projects about renewable energy technologies prevented to fully meet thematic promises in the development process. Moreover, two further questions exacerbated this challenge: given the available resources what is the right number of different age groups and, above all, when should children move to the next level? These questions arose after one year and answers to them also influenced the reuse of workshop content and the need to constantly develop new content.

The permanent, partly consecutive character with the necessity of several sessions of the same workshops led to problems if children could not participate steadily. Trainers had to deal with children's absences e.g. due to illnesses or mid-session re-joining, which disrupted the flow of workshops and impeded adequate support to other children. Sometimes this was enforced by the initial incomprehension of workshop roles of new trainers. Finally, the gradual development of the same participating children made it possible to work on more sophisticated projects with more dangerous machines. The trainer had hence, to balance a high skill level of more demanding children with safety and legal requirements. There was a shortage of experienced trainers for taking over this role and implementing dangerous machines in workshops.

Although safety issues are reported in several studies (Herrick & Klein, 2016), additional peculiarities complicated the permanent maker groups initiative. One problem resulted from the progressive increase of children's skills in the permanent groups. These children, especially the younger ones, tended hence, to overestimate themselves and being less cautious, which required special attention by the trainers. Further, the risk of injury increased when using dangerous machines or working in small group projects. The existing adult makerspace infrastructure as homebase was deemed too dangerous for children, and existing adult safety concepts were not suitable or sufficient. Insurances offered by specialized agencies never covered all potential risks, necessitating the development of adequate child-specific safety concepts.

Beyond these difficulties, the permanent group approach encountered similar organizational issues evidenced by other studies (Moorefield-Lang, 2014). Parental involvement presented one set of these challenges. Some parents were unreliable, failing to cancel their children's participation in a timely manner. Parents were seen as a temporary resource, as their involvement was limited to the duration of their children's participation. Therefore, the parental involvement needed to be balanced to get their commitment while avoid overwhelming them. Hence, managing expectations and communication with parents was difficult.

On the other hand, organizational issues included the high founding effort required for one person alone, the lack of voluntary persons, and the difficulty in finding long-term committed volunteers. Trainers were rarely available for exchange, and communication and coordination were challenging due to the use of multiple channels. Ensuring GDPR compliance and managing sensitive data, such as children's allergies, was also problematic. The initiative struggled with the organization, planning, and visibility of workshops, and community work was time-consuming. Moreover, infrastructure limitations, such as the lack of storage areas and the need for child-friendly tools, further constrained the initiative.

Finally, similar to other extra-scholastic initiatives social and diversity barriers characterized the approach of permanent groups, too. The target group, i.e. participating children, was not diverse enough as only few girls and no child from socio-economically disadvantaged classes joined the permanent groups. The initiative primarily reached children from upper-middle-class backgrounds, which limited its inclusivity.

6.3 Challenges in School Workshops

School workshops faced structural and resource-related problems that partly resulted from the specific constellation of this initiative (cf. Figure 4). The high technical preparation effort and the difficulty in adapting workshops developed for permanent groups to school settings were notable challenges. The specific focus on renewable energy technologies combined with making activities required a substantial budget due to high material costs. The aim to provide unique, stand-alone workshops to schools was further aggravated by large and varying numbers of children per class usually exceeded the existing infrastructure developed for the permanent groups. Managing schools' participation was difficult as information overload in schools and the scheduling of workshops outside regular school hours further complicated their participation. Above all, a key hindrance was the reachability of the workshop facility for wide-spread schools, including their timely arrival at workshop locations by using public transportation in the fragmented region of Steyr.

Despite having established a notable pool of volunteer trainers for the permanent groups, their participation in school workshops appeared as another limitation. Their motivation to conduct school workshops was low, missing the community flair, and the complexity of involving additional trainers and stakeholders added to this challenge. On the other hand, these extra recruited professional pedagogues lacked technical competences necessary for the thematic and methodological aspiration, and their scheduling flexibility was limited, too. Above, this compilation of trainers for school workshops induced tension between volunteer work and financial compensation of the professional pedagogues. Building a separate mid-term pool of trainers for school workshops was, hence, straining.

6.4 Challenges in Summer Workshops

Summer workshops as third approach, characterized by their event nature, faced structural and communicative barriers (cf. Figure 5). The effort required for accounting and reporting was substantial, and the high fees demanded by professional trainers limited the content of workshops. Similar to the school workshop format, the participation of coaches of the permanent groups was very limited. As the implementation was in summer, schools were not open and hence, socio-economically disadvantaged groups could not adequately be reached. The inclusion of girls was possible although challenging, and overall talented children tended to participate in the offered workshops. Communication of projects workshops through various channels as initial mean to reach different groups, was strained because the sheer quantity of workshops in which the project one's were embedded, made it difficult to visualize their content beyond simple photos.

Concerning the demand renewable energy topics were previously under-required. However, the limited supply due to lacking STEM-trainers with maker aspirations, were far more decisive for participation in workshops with this theme than the demand. To this thematic focus, the event nature of summer workshops only allowed a first contact with the topic without any depth.

However, the most notable novel issues in this summer workshop format were the pressure parents put on their children due to their ambition and need for supervision, leading to signs of burn-out of kids. Linked to the children's well-being a further problem arose, namely simply the heat characterizing meanwhile our summer periods which made children suffering.

7 Solution approaches

In the framework of this study, possible solutions were investigated through the interviews with stakeholders and trainers. There are no single specific measures that stand out as a solution; rather, a bundle and their combination seem to counteract the identified challenges. A broad range of actions were suggested by the key informants such as leveraging synergies, reciprocity and expectation management, impact demonstration, trainers' involvement in financial responsibility, continuous broad networking, transparency, pedagogical advice, mutual supportive culture, and co-creation events. All proposals are aligned to the specific challenges and summarized in figure 6 of the appendix. First attempts were already made to implement some solution approaches. However, as the project is still very young, the effectiveness of none of these solution attempts and proposals can be tested on an evident basis. Nevertheless, the list of actions may be helpful to other initiatives reacting on upcoming problems.

Given that the permanent format presented unique challenges distinct from earlier initiatives, the following discourse elaborates on the solutions that were proposed to address these specific issues.

Differentiated skill levels among children: The observed challenge of varying skill levels and engagement of participating children was considered with a rotation-based system with differently complex maker stations. However, when such a system is not feasible due to the early development phase of the group, trainers have begun to use open-ended tasks, optional extensions, and peer support mechanisms. These allow children to enter projects at different difficulty levels and progress at their own pace, without overwhelming beginners or underchallenging advanced participants.

Development and preparation effort and trainer expectations: The permanent format required continuous introduction of new workshops. The steady enlargement of the trainer pool and involvement of workshop scouts helped to keep pace with the necessary development requirements. To address the significant time needed for workshop preparation, a shared digital repository of adaptable workshop modules and documentation formats is being set up. While still in its early stages, this is intended to lower the preparation workload without limiting creative freedom, and to support knowledge exchange among trainers.

Safety and Legal Compliance: As children progress and work with more advanced tools and machines, safety and legal compliance become increasingly relevant. To meet these requirements, a liability insurance has been taken out and a modular safety training system has been developed. It includes safety introductions to children, regular safety data sheets adapted to machines acquired, supervised starter training to new coaches, the adaptation of a first-aid course aligned to the equipment used with the children and the inclusion of a supplementary novel child protection concept including risk analysis, prevention and dealing with suspected cases. These measures are designed to raise trainers' and children's awareness of potential risks while also aligning with recent Austrian regulations for youth protection and risk prevention.

Trainer Motivation and Continuity: Trainer motivation and continuity were identified as further challenges, particularly in light of the long-term commitment required. To support retention and knowledge transfer, a peer mentoring model is currently being tested. More experienced trainers accompany newcomers through co-facilitation or shadowing sessions. This not only strengthens trainer relationships but also helps establish consistent workshop routines and shared expectations. Trainers are invited to switch between the different roles of workshop developer, coach or simply accompanier.

Parental Involvement and Planning Reliability: Parental involvement proved to be both essential and difficult to manage. To strengthen communication and gain more reliable feedback, the project is trialing a structured parent feedback loop after each workshop cycle in an informal and formal way. This helps trainers better understand family expectations and encourages stronger ties between the initiative and the families involved, without placing excessive demands on parents.

These strategies emerged from internal feedback sessions and semi-structured interviews with trainers. While they are not yet fully validated through longitudinal outcomes, they reflect grounded, practice-informed approaches to complex challenges.

8 Practical implications for other initiatives

The findings from the Junior Maker Pioneers initiative provide valuable insights that can inform the development and implementation of similar initiatives aimed at engaging children in hands-on learning activities with a focus on renewable energy technology. These insights can help other initiatives address common problems and enhance their effectiveness. Most importantly, the identified challenges strongly relate to the different formats of sub-initiatives, such as permanent maker groups, school workshops, and summer events. Initiatives should therefore, tailor their strategies to address the unique challenges of each format based on different settings and frameworks (Mersand, 2021).

From a practical standpoint, the permanent groups formed the core of the Junior Maker Pioneers initiative. They offered the richest basis for reflection and interviews, from which context-specific approaches could be derived. These strategies are not universally applicable but represent grounded responses informed by field experience.

From a research perspective, long-term maker formats are rarely addressed in literature, which tends to emphasize short-term interventions. The sustained character of the permanent groups introduced unique demands in terms of workshop development, trainer engagement, and legal responsibilities.

9 Limitations and further research possibilities

This study on the JMP initiative has several limitations that should be acknowledged and may open avenues for future research. First, the findings are based on a relatively small sample size, primarily involving trainers and stakeholders directly associated with the initiative. This limited sample may not fully capture the diversity of experiences and perspectives in other similar initiatives. Further research could involve larger, more diverse samples to enhance generalizability.

Second, the study was geographically conducted in Steyr, Austria which may influence the applicability of the findings to other regions with different cultural, economic, and educational contexts. Comparative studies in various geographical settings could provide a broader understanding of the challenges and lead to best practices and sharing beyond borders. Third, the specific focus on renewable energy technologies may have influenced the types of challenges encountered and may not be applicable in settings with different thematic focuses. Future research could explore initiatives with similar themes in the area of sustainability to identify common and unique challenges.

Moreover, the study was conducted over a limited timeframe, which may not capture the long-term sustainability beyond the project's duration. Longitudinal studies are hence, needed to assess the enduring effects of makerspace initiatives for children. Finally, the reliance on qualitative methods, such as semi-structured interviews and reflection reports, may introduce subjectivity and bias in the findings. Incorporating quantitative research methods, such as surveys and experimental designs, would complement the qualitative findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impacts (Bryman, 2016).

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the use of MS Copilot for rephrasing and language correction support during the preparation of this paper.

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Appendix

Figure 2: First order codes and second order categories of challenges across all formats

Figure 3: First order codes and second order categories of challenges in permanent maker groups

Figure 4: First order codes and second order categories of challenges in school workshops

Figure 5: First order codes and second order categories of challenges in summer workshops

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Figure 6: Solution Approaches aligned to Challenges of all formats

